

SMART ERA PROJECT - EIP AGRI PRACTICE ABSTRACTS

IMPROVING ACCESS TO HEALTH SERVICES FOR RESIDENTS AND TOURISTS

The project addresses the issue of limited access to healthcare services in nine villages on the Devetaki Plateau. Health services in this rural area are difficult to access due to **poor organisation** and a **lack of public transport**. This particularly affects the inhabitants of the nine villages, but also tourists. It impedes social inclusion, demographic growth and local economic development. In addition to limited access to healthcare, a **lack of knowledge and expertise** means that people travel to see their GP unnecessarily, putting **extra pressure on doctors**.

To address these issues, **Sevlievo Municipality** and the **Devetaki Plateau Association (DPA)** held co-creation workshops with stakeholders to develop a Smart Innovation Package (SIP). The SIP includes a **user-friendly telemedicine tool** for delivering health services remotely, enabling patients to consult doctors, receive diagnoses and monitor their health without visiting a hospital. This will improve access to medical care, particularly in remote areas, and enable a faster emergency response. The package also provides **information and lectures** on the most common diseases in rural areas, as well as **advice** on healthy living, food and the use of natural products. Municipalities, NGOs and medical associations can adapt and use this model if they:

1. **ensure the participation of all** stakeholders.
2. establish **partnerships**.
3. **plan** activities **in advance**.
4. perform **tests**.

GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION

Benefits for end users:

- The elderly and families with children benefit from **more accessible health services**.
- Tourists get **faster access to information and responses** in the event of injury or accidents.
- General **practitioners and specialists experience less pressure**.
- The community has **access to** systematic, user-friendly **information**.

The main **costs** are related to coordination and setting up the digital infrastructure, but these can be minimised through partnerships and public funding.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Facilitating elements:

- **Community involvement** in all stages of the project to build motivation and trust
- **Partnership** between the three municipalities in the region and the DPA
- Use of **co-creation and facilitation tools**

Barriers:

- **Administrative burden** in the existing health system and personal data management
- **Conservatism** of some users and the medical community towards innovation
- **Different levels of knowledge and skills** among users to apply and use technological solutions
- **Limited long-term funding** for the maintenance and upgrading of the technological service

Message to end users:

Although part of a national policy, **access to health services can be brought closer to rural areas through innovation**. Provided there is partnership and commitment from local authorities, the community, NGOs and professional stakeholders, smart solutions can be found and implemented in small villages. Participation and lifelong learning can help to improve quality of life, reverse negative demographic trends and promote local and economic development.

ADDITIONAL MATERIALS

[Devetaki Plateau, Central North Bulgaria website](#)

[News on local workshops to co-design a Smart Innovation Package](#)

[News on SIP CO-CREATION WORKSHOP IN KRAMOLIN](#)

[SIP CO-CREATION WORKSHOP IN BRESTOVO AND KARPACHEVO](#)

